

LOOKING FOR RELIABLE TAXI BOOKING SERVICES?

SWITCH TO
BHUUMI
RIDESHARING
APP!

The Infinite Portal

BHUUMI RIDE

BHUUMI Ride is a new taxi-hailing app in South Carolina that provides comfortable, affordable rides and uses the latest technology while empowering its drivers.

With a wide network of registered taxi and drivers, the app allows its users to choose their ride and get to their desired location without having to worry about expensive taxi bills or their safety.

CHOOSE YOUR PREFERRED RIDE

BHUUMI RIDE COMES UP WITH
DIFFERENT RIDE OPTIONS TO
CHOOSE FROM. PASSENGERS
CAN CHOOSE:

Enter your mobile
no. to get start!

BHUUMI X

For economy rides up to 4 passengers

BHUUMI XL

For larger vehicle up to 6 passengers

BHUUMI LUX

For luxury cars up to 4 passengers

BHUUMI VAN

For luxury cars up to 4 passengers

EMPOWERS THE DRIVERS

The ridesharing app helps the drivers to become entrepreneurs while earning a respectful and sustainable livelihood. BHUUMI does not take any money from the customers as the payment goes directly to the drivers after the completion of each ride.

EASY BOOKING PROCESS

To get started, all you need to do is open the BHUUMI Ride App and it will show your location. You can enter your destination, choose your vehicle, and book your ride. The App will show your driver's picture, vehicle info, and provide you with an OTP. You can then check the arrival details, track your driver's location, and get started with the ride upon the driver's arrival. On completion of the ride, the user pays drivers directly whether online or cash.

PAY THE NOMINAL CHARGES ONLY

WITH BHUUMI, YOU DON'T HAVE TO WORRY ABOUT LONG TAXI BILLS! COMPARED TO OTHER SERVICE PROVIDERS, BHUUMI RIDESHARING APP IS CHEAPER. BHUUMI HAS NO SURGE PRICING AND THUS, YOU CAN ENJOY FLAT RATES FOR ALL LOCATIONS THROUGHOUT THE DAY.

GET SAFER RIDES

BHUUMI Ride has several added safety features to ensure extra security at every step of your ride, such as a personalized BHUUMI Driver ID and Driver Stickers for each driver.

ABOUT GET SERVICES THAT GET BETTER WITH TIME FONT

BHUUMI ride believes that improving services is an ongoing process, the team is consistently working to monitor the safety standards and services to upgrade them from time to time.

HOW TO GET IN TOUCH

Phone Number | 843-981-4411

Email Address | support@bhumi.com

Website | www.bhumiride.com

CONTACT INFORMATION

DOWNLOAD APPS ON GOOGLE PLAY AND APP STORE

Google Play

App Store